

Sloshing fluid-structure interaction and induced damping effects: modelling and experimental analysis

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Abstract

All aircraft are subjected to dynamics loads resulting from in-flight atmospheric gusts and turbulence, with the resulting stresses determining the sizing, and hence weight, of the resulting structure. There is much interest in studying active and passive approaches to alleviate these loads, leading to more fuel-efficient and environmentally friendly airplane designs. Recent work, as part of the H2020 SLOW-D project, has considered the use of fuel sloshing as a means of loads reduction, with fundamental transient response experiments, performed using a single degree of freedom system coupled to a liquid filled tank, demonstrating a multi-regime piecewise linear damping behaviour dependent on the amount of tank fill and the size of the excitation. This work continues the effort to improve the development of coupled fluid-structure sloshing models through investigation of the 2nd and 3rd transient response regions. Experimental measurements based on high frame-rate videos of the fluid surface motion and the tank vibration are used to further develop coupled structure / sloshing fluid computational models based on an SPH approach. A good comparison between the numerical model and the experimental measurements is found.

1 Introduction

All aircraft are subjected to dynamic loads resulting from in-flight atmospheric gusts and turbulence, with the resulting stresses determining the sizing, and hence weight, of the resulting structure [1]. There is much interest in developing active [2] (using the control surfaces) and passive (including composite tailoring [3] and folding wing-tips [4]) approaches to alleviate these loads, leading to more fuel-efficient and environmentally friendly airplane designs. Recent work, as part of the H2020 SLOW-D project, is considering the use of fuel sloshing as a means of reducing the loads effect of gusts and turbulence via increased damping. This research has used a combined numerical modelling and experimental approach.

In the civil engineering field, there have been many cases of using liquid sloshing as a tuned damper to reduce the lateral response of tall buildings to the wind or earthquakes [5, 6]; however, the majority of investigations have been concerned with sloshing in a lateral direction. Some works have considered damping in vertical vibratory systems with extensive work being carried out on particle impact damping, where energy is dissipated through momentum exchange between particles of different sizes and the structure [7]. Vertically excited systems containing liquids have also been studied previously, with applications such as liquid propellant tanks or water towers [8, 9, 10].

Relatively little work has considered the use of fuel sloshing for loads alleviation in aircraft structures, with preliminary studies focused on numerical investigations on integration of fuel sloshing in aeroelastic models [11]. Tuned mass dampers are often used in civil aircraft to reduce the vibration and noise associated with engines [12] or aeroelastic response [13], but they tend to consist of mechanical systems rather than sloshing of a fluid in a tank and have not been applied to gust or turbulence loads.

There is a need to be able to develop validated mathematical models of the coupled wing and fuel-sloshing process to enable exploitation of the potential added damping benefits of the sloshing motions via novel wing or tank designs. In particular, the use of smoothed particle hydrodynamics (SPH) and equivalent mechanical

model (EMM) methods in fluid sloshing and fluid-structure interaction research is well established [14] and these have been employed by the authors previously [15]. Especially successful in modelling free-surface flows, smoothed particle hydrodynamics is a CFD technique based upon a Lagrangian description of fluid mechanics. Originally developed in 1977 for astrophysical problems [16, 17], the SPH method has seen widespread adoption across a wide range of fluids dynamics application.

Previous experiments as part of the SLOW-D project have considered the overall transient acceleration response of a cantilever beam [18, 19] and a single DOF “T-beam” system [15] subjected to vertical sloshing motion. It was found that the presence of the fluid significantly increases the inherent damping in the system, but this is dependent upon the filling level of the tank and the intensity of motion. The maximum amount of damping was achieved at a 50% fill level and the system showed three distinct piece-wise linear damped response regimes during the transient decay related to different motions of the fluid. The T-beam study [15] concentrated upon the first response regime, immediately at the start of the transient response, where the fluid motion is turbulent and involves significant impacts of the fluid on the tank floor and ceiling. The experiments were compared with numerical simulations using SPH and EMM (based upon a bouncing ball model) to model the fluid motion and both methods gave a reasonable representation of the experimental results, particularly for the initial damping zone.

This paper builds upon the previous work [15] considering the T-beam vertical transient experiments, using video capture of the free fluid surface motion and the tank vertical displacement to further develop the coupled structure-sloshing fluid SPH and EMM computational models and understanding of the underlying physics. Emphasis is placed on the 2nd and 3rd damping regions which are dominated by the symmetric lateral sloshing motion of the fluid. Further comparisons between the mathematical models and the experimental measurements are also made.

2 Experimental setup

Previous work [15] involved a fundamental investigation into the effect of liquid sloshing on the transient response of the single DOF vertically vibrating structure represented in figure 1b. The motivation behind this configuration was to obtain a simplified vibrating system that isolates the dominant vertical motion associated with gust-excited wings. Ideally, such a system should be constrained to move only in the vertical z direction, should have linear stiffness and be lightly damped to facilitate the investigation of sloshing-induced damping. The idealized system and its implementation are represented in figure 1.

In order to achieve vertical lightly damped motion at high amplitudes, the configuration presented in figure 1b was used. Two steel strips joined together to form a single “T”-shaped structure were used. The two strips provide the stiffness of the system (k) and their joints are the main source of underlying (dry-structure) damping (c). A rectangular tank (height $H = 20\text{mm}$, width $w = 60\text{mm}$ and depth $d = 30\text{mm}$) with water inside is fitted in the middle of the horizontal beam. In order to avoid the hardening effect associated with clamped-clamped beams when subjected to deformations greater than the beam thickness [20], the T-beam allows for an in-plane displacement as well as for a rotation of the joining point. This configuration was found to allow for deflections as large as 14 times the beam thickness while still remaining in the linear stiffness domain [15]. All of the tests presented in this paper are step release tests with a maximum amplitude of 14 mm and either 50% filling level or no liquid (dry structure) and the mass of the system is kept constant at all times.

The system described has the properties presented in table 1. The 1dof equivalent mass ($m_{eq} = 276\text{ g}$) of the system is calculated using the measured frequency $f = 10.05\text{ Hz}$ and stiffness $k = 1.1\text{ N/mm}$. The dry structure damping is calculated from the acceleration data. Since a slight nonlinearity in damping is observed experimentally, the corresponding representative damping ratio was found to be in the range between 0.23% and 0.34% of the critical damping, as seen in the dry structure acceleration envelope in figure 1c. This nonlinearity is however deemed negligible in the analysis presented here.

The sloshing-induced damping effect can best be seen by studying the envelope of either the acceleration, velocity or displacement signals. Two typical acceleration envelopes are presented in figure 1c, for the 50% filling level and the dry structure cases. Multiple damping regimes can be identified, corresponding

Figure 1: Schematic representations of idealized and implemented SDOF structures and typical T-beam damping results

Table 1: Properties of T-beam system

m_{eq} [kg]	276×10^{-3}
ζ [%]	0.23 – 0.34
k [N/m]	1100
f [Hz]	10.05

to different linear regions on the log plot, and the damping ratio is calculated from the slope of each linear region, included in figure 1c as well. Previous work has emphasized the correlation between the different damping zones and the physical behaviour of the fluid, as seen in figure 1c and categorised as:

- Region 1 (R1) - turbulent vertical fluid motion
- Region 2 (R2) - symmetric lateral sloshing motion
- Region 3 (R3) - small fluid activity following the tank base motion

This paper presents the identification of the free surface of the fluid in the tank during the transient decays and concentrates on understanding and modelling the fluid behaviour in damping zones R2 and R3.

3 Free surface identification methodology

In order to properly analyze the liquid sloshing under parametric excitation the surface of the liquid must be identified automatically in every frame. High-speed footage has been collected for the 50% fill level case, at a frame rate of 480 frames per second. The footage was then post processed using the Matlab Image Processing and Signal Processing Toolboxes [21].

Figure 2: The mark image used to transform the global frame of reference to the local tank frame of reference with the help of the correlation coefficients between the reference mark image and each frame

The camera is stationary and the tank is oscillating. In order to facilitate the identification of water surface and to allow consistent comparisons between different frames, the coordinate system must be changed to a local one; in other words, the tank must be identified in each frame and cropped out. This is done by searching for the point of maximum cross-correlation [22] between the matrices corresponding to each frame and a mark image – a reference image to be identified in each frame. In order to eliminate estimation errors between different frames, the mark image must be distinct, must possess complex features and be present entirely in each frame. The weights attached to the structure were found to give the best results in this case. The tank is identified in each frame at a fixed distance from the point of maximum cross-correlation, as the structure is assumed to be rigid. This procedure is exemplified in figure 2, where the mark image is used to correctly identify the tank in three maximum amplitude positions. The measure of matching between each frame and the mark image is presented in the form of normalized cross-correlation coefficients with values between -1 and 1, representing negative and positive correlation. A matrix of coefficients can be formed, with each entry corresponding to the level of correlation at each point in the frame matrix. An example is provided in figure 2 where the point of maximum correlation between the reference image and a representative frame corresponds to the entry of maximum value in the matrix and is marked by the red dot.

The displacement of the tank is tracked as well via the point of maximum cross-correlation between the mark image and each frame. An example of such tracking is shown later in figure 4 for both dry structure and 50% filling level.

Once the tank is consistently identified, a series of image transformations are applied to each frame in order to isolate the surface of the sloshing liquid. The consistent and automatic identification of the sloshing free surface from experimental footage is a valuable tool for post-processing experimental data. Classically, probes mounted on fixtures on the top of the tank that extend into the water volume are used to measure surface displacement at one point. The main advantages of a procedure based on image processing are its non-invasive nature and the possibility to measure surface displacements at all points; such techniques have been successfully used in the past (e.g. [23, 24]). Notably, Jiang et al. [25] made use of a combination of laser-based high speed imaging together with an edge detection program and a capacitance wave probe to precisely quantify the movement of the free surface. Particular to the procedure presented here is that, on the one hand, no distinct markers or dye is used and, on the other hand, the 3D effects are handled robustly. The main sources of three-dimensional effects in the experiment presented here are given by the interaction of the fluid with the corners of the tank (also shown to be problematic in [23]) and with the front and back panels. Unlike usual image-processing based techniques, no clear contrast between the fluid and the background is present in this experiment and instead multiple filtering and averaging steps are employed to robustly identify the sloshing liquid surface. This process involves multiple steps presented in figure 3 and can be detailed as follows:

1. Each frame is converted into a grayscale format in order to obtain a 2D matrix. The grayscale image is then converted into a matrix with only 0 and 1 entries – the image is *binarized* in order to facilitate the identification of high-contrast regions, necessary for the next step.
2. The binarized image is used for the identification of all white regions – clusters of 1 entries in the frame matrix. This is done using a modified Moore-Neighbor tracing algorithm as implemented in Matlab under the *bwboundaries* function [26].
3. A first level of filtering concerns the boundaries far out of the areas where the water surface might be found. A substantial number of the identified boundary points are part of the tank or of water drops on the ceiling of the tank. Since these regions are not part of the surface, they are eliminated from each frame. Small-sized boundaries (less than 50 points) are also eliminated, as these are, in this study, more often than not situated outside of the water surface.
4. At this point the majority of the identified points are part of the sloshing surface; however, it is still not sufficiently distinct. Even a small number of points outside the surface region can lead to significant errors in surface estimation, especially around the lateral boundaries of the fluid in this particular experiment. In order to improve the results, a fourth degree polynomial is fitted over the identified points. The distance from each point and the polynomial is calculated and all points out of the selected band ($\pm 40\%$ in this study) around the curve are eliminated. A polynomial degree of 4 was used for the polynomial as this was found to provide an adequate global approximation of the surface point cluster.
5. In order to further reduce the number of relevant points and to mitigate the 3D sloshing effects, a mean value of the points' z coordinates at each x station is computed and used further.
6. The points identified until now are still relatively scattered and clustered along the z axis, since they are obtained from boundaries of different sizes and locations. A Savitzky-Golay (S-G) polynomial filter [27] is used to smooth the data, as implemented under the *sgolayfilt* function in Matlab. Cubic functions are locally fitted on sets of 251 points out of a typical set of 712 points (the number may differ slightly from one frame to another). At the same time, if there exists any x station without a point associated with it, points from the previous frame are filled in at the respective stations. This is done in order to both preserve continuity between frames and to account for situations where the contrast is not adequate and boundaries on the binarized image are not correctly identified. This is not the case in the example presented in figure 3.
7. Considering that at the previous step new points have been potentially added to the identified water surface, similarly to step 4, a new fourth degree polynomial is fitted over the data to filter out any outliers. This is particularly important around the meniscus zones, where significant errors are introduced

Figure 3: Sloshing surface identification methodology

by ill-identified points associated with the left and right hand side domain boundaries. In this case, the points outside of the $\pm 10\%$ band around the curve are eliminated.

8. A final S-G smoothing of the data is done to include the potentially newly added points from the previous frames (step 6), using cubic functions fitted over sets of 201 points. A lower number of points is used for the S-G filtering compared to step 6 since the data at this stage are closer to the final identified surface and smoothing over a higher number of points would lead to unnecessary local feature attenuation. After this final step the water surface is considered identified for the current frame and the algorithm proceeds to the following frame.

4 1DOF SPH numerical model

Within this work, SPH is employed to model the sloshing behaviour and compare it against the experimentally identified sloshing responses. SPH provides a Lagrangian description of fluid mechanics, such that a fluid is discretised into a set of particles. A localised interpolation is constructed to evaluate field variables

and thus the equations governing fluid motion such that particles can be integrated forward in time. As particles are free to interact and move according to their governing equations, no explicit treatment of the free surface is required which simplifies the process of modelling liquid sloshing.

Here, the essential SPH interpolants shall be presented with application to the pressure gradient driving fluid motion, however, for a complete description of the SPH method see [28]. This fundamental interpolation is simply a convolution between the chosen function ($f(\mathbf{x})$) and a function that approximates the Dirac-delta function, taking the following form when discretised as a summation over particles,

$$f(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx \sum_j^N f(\mathbf{x}_j) \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h). \quad (1)$$

W is known as the ‘smoothing kernel’ which has a length scale dependent on h the ‘smoothing length’. Equation 1 provides a smoothed representation of the chosen function at a particle (\mathbf{x}_i), depending on the local neighbourhood of N particles which have mass (m) and density (ρ). Indices i and j designate the particle at which variables are being evaluated and one of its neighbours, respectively. A classical use of this within SPH is to substitute $f(\mathbf{x})$ with the density,

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx \sum_j^N m_j W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h), \quad (2)$$

giving the SPH density estimator; which simply allows a particles density to be approximated as a spatially weighted summation over local particle masses. Spatial derivatives of the field function can be evaluated through a similar interpolation [28],

$$\nabla f(\mathbf{x}_i) \approx - \sum_j^N f(\mathbf{x}_j) \frac{m_j}{\rho_j} \nabla W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h), \quad (3)$$

where ∇W is the gradient of the smoothing function. With equation 3 it is possible to derive particle accelerations by considering the inviscid momentum equation for a fluid,

$$\frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = -\frac{\nabla P}{\rho} \implies \frac{D\mathbf{u}_i}{Dt} = - \sum_j^N m_j \left[\frac{P_j}{\rho_j^2} + \frac{P_i}{\rho_i^2} \right] \nabla W(\mathbf{x}_i - \mathbf{x}_j, h). \quad (4)$$

Note, the pressure gradient $\nabla P/\rho$ is expanded to give a symmetric form of the SPH discretisation, ensuring linear and angular momentum is conserved between particles. Inclusion of an equation of state, a constitutive equation relating fluid density and pressure (P), completes the system of equations. Forming what is known as the weakly compressible SPH method, which would otherwise require solution of a pressure-Poisson equation for an incompressible solution. An additional viscosity term is included within the momentum equation (4) and time integration is performed using the Newmark-beta method. For further details regarding this formulation see reference [15].

As the position of fluid is exactly known within numerical methods, surface detection is trivial in comparison to the experimental approach. The method employed compares two geometric properties of the particle distribution, the mass-weighted average distance of a particle’s neighbours and the number of neighbours. A surface particle is therefore defined when the condition,

$$\frac{\alpha}{h} \left\| \frac{\sum_j m_j \mathbf{x}_j - m_j \mathbf{x}_i}{\sum_j m_j} \right\| + \beta > N_{neighbours,i} \quad (5)$$

is true, where α and β provide a linear relationship between the two geometric properties according to reference [29]. If a particle has a low number of neighbours for a relatively nominal spatial distribution it can be assumed to lie on the surface. This provides a robust method for surface detection at no additional

Figure 4: Identified displacement time series comparison, dry structure vs. 50% fill level

computational cost.

As the fluid response is strongly coupled to the tank motion, a structural model is required to move the SPH boundaries according to the T-Beam response. A partitioned approach to fluid-structure interaction is employed here, such that the structural model can be solved independently using its own spatial discretisation. In this case, the T-Beam is idealised as a SDOF structure allowing use of a simple spring-mass-damper oscillator [15]. Coupling is performed using a strong coupling methodology, which synchronises the structural and fluid domains at every numerical time instance, ensuring energy is conserved within the system.

5 Results

The surface tracking methodology to post-process experimental sloshing footage and a numerical model were used to produce a series of results which are now discussed, in time and frequency domains, focusing on both the qualitative and quantitative behaviour of the sloshing fluid during its motion in the first symmetric sloshing mode. This mode of fluid motion was shown to be correlated to substantial energy dissipation in the coupled system.

As discussed in section 3, the overall tank movement was tracked as an intrinsic part of the global to local frame of reference transformation. The variation of the tank displacement with respect to time was obtained and is presented in figure 4 for the dry case and 50% fill level. One important aspect that these results show is that significant damping is introduced in the system when the fluid interacts with the tank. Moreover, three different sloshing regimes can be identified as presented in figure 5, each of which displays a particular qualitative sloshing patterns, as well as different damping ratios due to the sloshing-induced dynamics. The amplitude of the tank is significantly reduced throughout the R1 region, from 14 mm to approximately 3 mm for the 50% fill level case. The sloshing pattern associated with R2 was found to dampen the motion furthermore, with a damping ratio greater than that of the dry-structure, reducing the system's displacement furthermore from 3 mm to 0.4 mm. The third region was found to introduce negligible damping, equal to that of the dry-structure.

All of the above observations obtained on the basis of the displacement signal analysis derived from the image processing technique described in section 3 are consistent with previously obtained findings based on [15]. An example comparison between the identified displacement and acceleration envelopes is presented in figure 6. Here, a comparison is made between the displacement and acceleration envelope functions. The data are represented on a semi-logarithmic scale to facilitate the distinction between the three regions of damping. The straight lines on such a plot are indicative of viscous-like exponentially decaying damping behaviour. No units are included on the vertical axis, since displacement and acceleration data are compared.

Figure 5: Photos for a representative cycle in each damping region

Figure 6: Tank displacement vs. acceleration envelopes comparison, 50% fill level

Considering that the underlying vibrating mechanical system has only one degree of freedom, the displacement and acceleration envelopes should have the same shape, scaled by a $-\omega^2$ factor, where ω is the angular frequency of the system. This is indeed what is found; a very good agreement is observed between the two signals, strengthening the confidence in the data obtained via image processing.

The identified image data, however, contain other rich sources of information. For example, further valuable analysis of the fluid sloshing inside the tank can be based on studying the displacement of the fluid surface mid-point in the local (i.e. moving) tank frame of reference. The quantitative analysis is concentrated around the water surface mid-point since it oscillates with the highest amplitude. Considering the length of the tank $L = 60$ mm, this point is situated at the 30 mm mark on the x axis measuring from the left side of the tank. The amplitude of the motion of the mid-point, in the local moving fluid tank frame of reference, is plotted against time in figure 7, alongside the amplitude of the tank. The analysis, using the image processing described earlier, started at approximately the 3 seconds mark, when the vertical component of the fluid sloshing motion was reduced and the surface identification using the procedure presented in section 3 could be done. An important aspect characteristic of the sloshing of the fluid inside the tank is related to its own amplitude compared to that of- the tank itself. The sloshing amplitude is substantially larger than that of the tank in region R2 where the fluid oscillates in the first symmetric mode under parametric excitation conditions. The theoretical value of the first sloshing mode frequency in a rectangular tank [14], calculated

Figure 7: Water surface mid-point and tank displacement signals

based on the geometric characteristics of the tank and the water column height, is 4.7 Hz [15]. It is a well-known classical result that under parametric excitation a fluid inside such a tank will slosh at multiples of a half of the frequency of excitation [14], which in this case is 10.05 Hz. As shown later, the frequency content of the fluid surface motion indicates a strong component at 5.18 Hz (figure 8) which satisfactorily matches the expected half-frequency of the parametric excitation. This leads to the conclusion that the fluid inside the tank gets excited at a frequency closely matching its natural frequency which is associated with the first symmetric mode observed in figure 5 (region 2), leading to intense energy dissipation and, thus, substantially increased damping ratio observed in R2 when compared to R3.

Further insight into the behaviour of the liquid surface can be gained by studying the frequency content of the surface mid-point motion. The Fourier Transform of the mid-point displacement signal, normalized to the largest value, is presented in figure 8 alongside a time representation of the frequency content in the form of a spectrogram. A dominant frequency is observed at 5.18 Hz, close to half the parametric excitation frequency of 10.05 Hz. This is consistent with the classical findings related to parametric excitation and emergence of Faraday waves [14]. Multiple higher harmonics are observed as well albeit with a lower contribution. Further experimentation might be needed to establish the origin of these harmonics. For instance, they could be due to 3D effects via additional modes present in the sloshing fluid. It has been previously observed experimentally that low-amplitude harmonic and superharmonic sloshing motions can occur in the vicinity of unstable regions – regions where a certain sloshing mode starts to get parametrically excited. For example, Dodge *et al.* [30] observed that, in the context of low-frequency longitudinally excited cylindrical containers, “*large-amplitude free surface motions occur when the liquid responds as a one-half subharmonic of the excitation*” and that “*harmonic and superharmonic liquid surface motions are also observed, although their amplitudes are usually smaller than those corresponding to the one-half subharmonic response*”. Additionally, a sideband frequency of 4.8 Hz is observed, correlated with the amplitude modulation of the water surface mid-point signal evident in figure 7. Jiang *et al.* [25] noted the same amplitude modulation (beating effect) in the mid-point elevation in a similar experiment and they attributed this occurrence to environmental noise. In our case, the amplitude modulation might be related to several factors: a longitudinal wave component with a small contribution in the experimental data and more evident in the SPH simulations; small fluctuations in the frequency content of the system leading to time-varying phase differences between the vibrating tank and the sloshing fluid; three-dimensional effects stemming from supplementary modal contributions.

It is instructive to evaluate the frequency content variation in time as well. In the second part of figure 8 a spectrogram of the surface mid-point displacement signal is represented; a dashed black line showing the end of R2 and the start of R3 is included as well. The subharmonic 5 Hz component is present at all times

Figure 8: Frequency content of water surface mid-point displacement signal

together with the 10 Hz component, with a smaller contribution. While the two components mentioned are present at all times, a noticeable decrease in the higher frequency content is observed after the end of R2. This is correlated with a marked decrease in sloshing amplitude evident in figure 7, as well as with an important change in damping ratio, as seen in the piece-wise linear trends of the envelopes in figure 6.

A numerical SPH simulation was performed, and the identified free-surface motion compared to the experimental signal within the R2 and R3 regimes. In addition to the mid-point displacement, a statistical indicator based upon the Modal Assurance Criterion (MAC) [31] is calculated at every time instance to provide a measure of surface similarity between the two data sets. The normalised scalar product of the two vectors defining free-surface amplitudes at the same longitudinal positions is computed, which has a value of unity for exactly matching surfaces and tends toward zero for dissimilar shapes. Results for the mid-point displacement and MAC correlation are shown in figure 9, including selected snapshots of the identified surfaces.

Overall, there is good agreement between the numerical and experimental surface signals, with the correlation metric mostly remaining above 0.9. However, the mid-point deflection signal is somewhat dissimilar between the simulation and experiment during R2, with the aforementioned amplitude modulation having a significant presence. Unlike the experimental analysis, this can mostly be attributed to the distinct periodic emergence of the simulated longitudinal fluid waves at a frequency of approximately half the 5Hz first symmetric sloshing mode [14]. Despite being excited purely vertically, slight asymmetries in the initial conditions which develop throughout turbulent motion within the R1 regime result in the asymmetric behaviour. As these waves are not directly driven by tank motion, they would nominally be attenuated by the presence of surface tension which is not insignificant at the length scales considered here. However, with surface tension not modelled the formation of asymmetries and resulting nonlinearities are possible, such as the breaking wave shown within the second inset in figure 9, which is indicative of high Weber number flows (effectively infinite in the simulation). The build-up and interaction of these effects with the dominant parametric wave results in the beating behaviour observed. A time varying phase-shift is also induced, with the two wave forms becoming completely out-of-phase at 4.5-5.5 s, before returning to a better match within R3. This analysis has highlighted the requirement for appropriate surface tension and contact line dynamics modelling in order to achieve accurate numerical simulation of sloshing behaviour at length scales such as

Figure 9: Comparison between identified experimental and SPH free-surface midpoint displacements and correlation metric (MAC). Red and blue lines represent experimental and SPH surfaces, respectively.

these. Despite these errors, there exists a better correlation between the methods during R3, with amplitudes and frequencies mostly matching with a small persistent error resulting from the two menisci not being present within the numerical surface. Additionally, there is a noise present within the experimental signal not observed in the SPH, this is simply a result of the inherent difficulties to accurately discern the surface position through a dynamically changing meniscus and viewpoint.

6 Conclusions

Several aspects of the sloshing fluid behaviour inside a vertically freely vibrating tank have been investigated. As indicated in previous research, the sloshing pattern in such a system displays multiple clearly delineated regions, each associated with distinct qualitative behaviour as well as different values of damping ratio. This work presented post-processing tools based on experimental footage, image processing and a series of results obtained using these tools. Numerical models are developed to complement the experimental investigations and to provide insight into the physics of the sloshing problem. Results of a computational method were compared against the experimentally identified surface behaviour, showing good agreement aside from the emergence of longitudinal wave motion, likely due to the absence of surface tension in the numerical formulation. The lateral motion of the fluid associated with the first symmetric sloshing mode inside a rectangular tank was shown to significantly absorb energy from the vibrating system and, by means of the surface identification tools developed here, this motion can be better understood quantitatively. The oscillation of the liquid free surface has been investigated, showing a dynamic response characteristic of parametrically excited liquids. Overall good agreement between the numerical and experimental results was found, with discrepancies highlighting required improvements in the presented methods.

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